

can be raised year round with this system.

Bamboo platforms were attached to two large airtight oil drums. The tops of the rafts were covered with damaged gunny sacks and a thin 7.5-cm layer of rice soil was spread over the surface.

We compared the performance of 10 short-duration rice varieties on 3- × 3-m floating rafts with 3 replications. Seedlings were transplanted 18 d after seeding in Jun 1985 (wet season).

Crop growth was satisfactory (see table). □

Growth characteristics, yield attributes, and yield of rice varieties grown on floating rafts. Vellayani, India, 1985 kharif.

Variety	Height (cm)	Tillers/hill	Productive tillers/hill	Percentage of panicles/hill	Panicle length (cm)	Filled grains/panicle	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
Cul. 170	62	28	26	93	14	36	4.0	6.9
Cul. 8	92	27	23	85	18	30	4.0	6.7
Karthika	102	25	22	88	20	30	2.0	5.0
Mo-5	90	28	22	78	19	32	2.7	6.8
Pavizham	95	21	16	76	18	25	2.1	6.1
Mo-4	100	11	9	82	19	22	1.7	6.9
Triveni	102	21	18	82	19	39	4.6	6.4
Bhadra	82	18	16	89	17	32	2.7	6.8
Kochuvithu	110	14	10	71	20	21	2.0	5.5
Cul. 93	105	23	20	87	20.5	43	4.7	8.7

Effect of land preparation on control of *Paspalum distichum*

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We tested tillage to control perennial grass weed *Paspalum distichum* L. in transplanted rice in Guimba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines.

Total dry weed weight in unweeded plots was highest with 1 plowing + 3 harrowings by hand tractor; *Echinochloa glabrescens* Munro ex Hook. f. accounted for the bulk of the weed growth (see table).

The intensive soil turning by the hand tractor reduced growth of *P. distichum*, but not significantly. It could have brought seeds of *E. glabrescens* to the

surface or scarified them, resulting in increased germination and growth. Or, an allelopathic substance that might be released by *P. distichum* reduces growth of *E. glabrescens*. Tall-growing annual grass *E. glabrescens* also might have competed with and reduced growth of shorter *P. distichum*.

The significant yield reduction was the result of weed competition, probably because of increased growth of *E. glabrescens*. No significant yield differences were found in the plots treated with butachlor or hand weeded. This indicates that *P. distichum* can be reduced with good land preparation and the annual grass population that may increase can be checked by butachlor. □

Effect of modified urea materials and N levels on transplanted rice

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Split application of urea and modified urea materials was tested in 1985 kharif.

In a field experiment laid out on a deep Vertisol (pH 7.5, 0.61% organic C, CEC 20.6 meq/ 100 g, 25.3 kg available P (Olsen)/ ha, 4.6 meq exchangeable K/ 100 g, 0.2 ppm available Zn and silty clay texture). At the last puddling, 26.4

Effect of modified urea and N level on transplanted rice. Kota, India, 1985 kharif.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)
Control (no N)	2.2	181.3
58 kg N/ha PU-BS	3.9	214.8
PU-SS	3.9	213.3
SCU-basal	4.0	237.5
USG-placement	4.1	270.0
MPCU-basal	3.9	219.0
87 kg N/ha PU-BS	4.6	241.5
PU-SS	4.5	238.3
SCU-basal	5.9	269.8
USG-placement	6.1	270.3
MPCU-basal	4.8	249.8
116 kg N/ha PU-BS	6.0	287.8
PU-SS	5.8	296.3
SCU-basal	6.0	316.8
USG-placement	6.1	329.0
MPCU-basal	5.6	268.5
CD	(0.05) 0.338.3	

^aPU-BS = prilled urea, local best split, PU-SS = prilled urea, standard split, SCU-basal = sulfur-coated urea, USG-placement = urea supergranules, and MPCU-basal = Mussooriephospho-coated urea.

Total weed weight and weight of *Echinochloa glabrescens* and *Paspalum distichum* in the unweeded plots as affected by tillage levels, and grain yield as affected by different weeding regimes.^a Nueva Ecija, Philippines.

Tillage treatment	Weed weight (g/m ²)			Grain yield (t/ha)		
	<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i>	<i>Paspalum distichum</i>	Total	No weeding	Hand weeding (21 and 35 DT)	Butachlor (0.6,3 DT)
1 plowing + 3 harrowings (within 1 mo before transplanting)	180 a	30 a	274 a	2.1 a	2.7 a	2.6 ab
1 plowing + 3 harrowings (within 2 mo before transplanting)	159 a	37 a	259 a	1.9 a	2.6 a	2.2 b
1 plowing + 3 harrowings (harrowing by hand tractor)	418 b	8 a	578 b	0.9 b	2.4 a	2.6 ab
2 plowings + 3 harrowings (animal)	53 a	60 a	141 a	2.3 a	2.0 a	2.3 b
1 plowing + 5 harrowings (animal)	127 a	62 a	214 a	2.3 a	2.6 a	3.0 a

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. DT = days after transplanting.